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THE MYTHOLOGICAL IMAGES OF THE WITCH IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK FOLKLORE/LITERATURE

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Annotation. This article provides an overview of mythonyms and mythological images in English and Uzbek literature and focuses on the image of witch. In particular, the article details the facts about that the image of witches in various appearances and purposes in English myths and fairy tales as well as it analyzes information about the history of the emergence of the above mythologies.

Key words: myth, mythological images, British folklore, Uzbek legends, witches, traditions, culture.

“Mythological thinking is thinking that comes from the domination of the imagination,” say Y. Golosovker said, “Imagination is not the result of ordinary activity, but a form of higher thought, a form of both creativity and knowledge.” This phenomenon is also characteristic of the tabloid of mythological images. At the same time, in the imagination of our people there are a number of traditions, ceremonies associated with mythological images (giant, demon, lizard, fairy, humo, squirrel, semurg, etc.) and an important archeological page in the history of our people. There are findings, ethnographic data, which show that these images are not only a product of art, but also have their own historical basis. Accordingly,

it is appropriate to study the historical roots of mythological images, to make a comparative analysis of their mythological and historical features on the basis of folklore and written sources. The art of folklore plays an important role in the spread of myths, in their transmission from generation to generation, and they are mainly narrated through words, and as a result have survived to the present day.[1]

According to M.Juraev, “myth is a myth that originated in the earliest times of folklore and embodies the ideas of mankind about the world at that time, but also embodies the beliefs, textures, including the creation of the universe, the emergence of celestial bodies, plants. and the origin of the animal kingdom, the causes and essence of natural phenomena, includes the beliefs about mythical heroes, gods, and deities” (Juraev, 2017;15). The influence of myth and mythological views on the human mind is so powerful that it fascinates him and provides spiritual nourishment while ensuring that he travels to a fantastic world. At the same time, if it causes a person's childhood dreams and imaginary visit to the magical world, it will directly help and motivate someone to heroically pursue new dreams. [3]

Mythological pictures are the result of primordial creative fiction, which helped explain the reasons for supernatural powers the reasons of supernatural powers that exist in the human mind. Mythological images in folklore and written literature serve to show the full expression of artistic interpretation and the breadth of poetic thinking. As well as English mythology is a collection of myths that have emerged throughout British history. Myths are mainly based on Anglo-Saxon, Christian and Celtic mythologies and legends of the English tradition. There are also a variety of mythological images in British folklore. They serve to enhance artistic sensitivity as the main characters of myths and legends. Mythological images are considered to be the main heroes of British folklore and have been passed down from generation to generation through various sources for centuries. Even the views on some mythological images are noteworthy in that they are still preserved. The most common mythological images in British folklore are witches, elves, giants, trolls, goblins, dragons, which are also found in the folklore of other

nations. [4] Some, such as fairies, witches and dragons, can even be found in Uzbek folklore. It is amazing that many mythical imagery in English and Uzbek folklore and literature are identical, despite the fact that they speak different systematic languages and live on separate continents.. In this article, we would like to compare the image of witch. In particular, in English and Uzbek legends and fairy tales, the image of a witch is often described as a mythological image that combines negative features. In British folktale witches often described as a ugly, wart-nosed women huddling over a cauldron of boiling liquid or riding through the sky on brooms wearing pointy hat with green skin and always dressed in black. In English folklore witches live in abandoned areas or in the dark forests and set a trap for her prey. As well as the witches illustrated different in different myths, for instance, in King Arthur “Morgana La Fey” depicted as a evil woman with beautiful appearance but inner side is black, “Elphaba” is identified with the Wicked Witch of the West from L. Frank Baum’s 1900 novel The Wonderful Wizard of Oz, and. she is born with green skin and sharp teeth, and she behaved oddly.

Yalmogiz is a mythological character in the form of a bloodthirsty, man-eating, especially child-abducting, extremely ugly, hunched, scaly old woman. He is also interpreted as the leader of the giants. According to its appearance, the realities of the matriarchy period (the period of maternal fertility) created the ground. This mythological image is often found in Uzbek tales and legends. For example, the fairy tale “Yalmogiz kampir”. Besides, the very first version of written image of witch in Uzbek culture was “Surhayl kampir” in the novel “Alpomish”.

The importance of mythical imagery in both British and Uzbek tradition and literature cannot be overstated. For millennia, the mythical imagery listed above have been present in English myths, folklore, and fairy tales. These photos stand out for their variety and exceptional qualities. They have a distinct creative influence on the works they represent. It should also be noted that the image of a witch is regarded differently in English and Uzbek oral and written literature. As a

result, the image of a witch holds a distinct position in both cultures' folklore and written literature.

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola tarjima nazariyasi va hozirgi kunda unda sodir bo'layotgan muammolarga e'tibor beradi. Qolaversa, aloqa-aralashuv vositasi, uning turlari va tarjimada noverbal aloqa-aralashuv vositalariga duch kelganda paydo bo'ladigan qiyinchiliklar haqida fikr yuritilib, qiyosiy tahlil o'tkazish orqali mazmun-mohiyatini yoritib beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: til, tarjima, lisoniy aloqa-aralashuv vositalari, noverbal aloqa vositalari